

Interview Aviation Museum Kbely - Miroslav Khol
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

- Presentation of the institution :

The Aviation Museum Kbely is the national aviation museum, part of the Military History Institute. It is a military museum under the Ministry of Defence, but it also includes civilian airplanes in the collection. The seat of the museum complex is the historic military airport Prague – Kbely, the first air base built after the creation of Czechoslovakia in 1918. The exhibition relates directly to the history of Czechoslovak and Czech aviation, primarily military aviation. Miroslav Khol is Head of the museum.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project ? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection ? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach ? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

The Museum has 1 hangar about WWII aircrafts, with 6 airplanes on display (French, British, Russian, German). These aircrafts come from the National Technique Museum, they have been transferred in the late 60's at Kbely.

The museum has never been involved in wrecks recovery.

They have some small recoveries from the ground, mainly artefacts from bombers which landed. Some people bring artefacts to the museum, the museum accepts them all. An archaeologist as part of the staff for 2 years. These artefacts are presented in temporary exhibitions or kept in storage.

- Concept of “conservation” : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle ? How do you define long term ? What does the idea of “conservation” mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

When objects arrive, they go through quarantine before conservation.

As a general approach, the museum accepts the authenticity of the objects. Only removal of soil and dust but no wish for a new aspect, rather try to keep in original condition.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration?

Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

In general, there is a discussion between the curator of collections and the restorers. There is a group of restorers for airplanes and other groups for other types of collections, weapons for ex. Collaboration between the groups as well.

There is a branch for the maintenance of the collection : restorers, curators. Modern airplanes : collaboration with airforce technicians and technical means from the airbase.

Also some volunteers, many of them have Airforce background. Volunteers mainly take care of the maintenance of exhibits outside and aircrafts they know from their service in the Airforce.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

The 6 WWII aircrafts are complete, some restored in the past, but not in flying or working condition. They are kept in an original hangar from WWI, built on site in the 20's (classified building).

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

Permanent exhibition : Monitoring (HR & Temperature, also pollutants) with the team from the University as part of the Procraft project. This is something new fro the museum.. This hangar has fire signalization.

Too soon to say about the data.

Temporary exhibition : in another building, also with monitoring.

Storage : situated in another building 15 km south of Prague. At Military Technik Museum (hosts ground forces artefacts), in former military barracks. 3 new buildings in storage area, built in 2010 with control for HR and Temperature, and new fire extinguisher system.

Protection of museum collections is defined by Czech Law No. 122/2000 including temperature and humidity for different materials.

Temperature and humidity in our storage building are as follows: Temperature - 20 degrees C and Humidity 50 %. Which is corresponding with that Law.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

There has always been a focus for conservation of objects since the begining of the museum, in 1968. Knowledge is much better now, mainly about corrosion/degradation problems and possible treatments.

Participation in the 2018 conference in Linköping in Sweden. Important and good to have these connections. Conferences usually bring more questions than answers. For ex, the former chief conservator from Imperial War Museum had pointed out many risks associated with aviation objects, beyond corrosion, like insects, dangerous materials, etc.. The team in Kbely had a new eye on their own collections after this.

Hope that Procraft brings a little bit of answers.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

No problems with Al alloys in WWII collections, but more for the ones from the 50's which are kept outside.

Restorers reports from former interventions : some minor parts (instruments) have been replaced, new painting on some airplanes. Last airplane restored in 2008. Miroslav asks his colleagues about former treatments (see below).

The plywood structure of the Illiushin Il-2 (russian ground attack plane) has been restored by a private company.

The aluminium alloy panels were firstly treated by Bonderite products (see attachment below) and then painted by zinc chromate primer paint.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

The country was occupied by German forces in March 39. Lot of people and soldiers escaped and many also were executed.

Czech airmen flew all types of aircrafts, except Germans, during WWII.

After 1989 : people were more proud about their history, medals and celebrations of soldiers.

At the museum, WWII period is very interesting for visitors.

Normal visitors prefer the complet airplanes and reneactments with mannequins. Smaller objects are more interesting for aviation fans and historians.

Overall good interest for the WWII collections.

Same presentation approach for all the collections, no particular focus for WWII.

All nationalities are presented in an equal way, technical data, historical planes.

Conservation and restoration is very important for the head of the institution.

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